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COVER PAGE AND DECLARATION

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Students' Full Name:	Mony Ho
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E-SIGNATURE:

DATE:

13 June 2024

EIU Paris City Campus

Address: 59 Rue Lamarck, 75018 Paris, France | **Tel:** +33188320435 | **Mobile/WhatsApp:** +33607591197 | **Email:** paris@eiu.ac

EIU Operations HQ

Address: 16th Fl. Amarin Tower, 496-502, Room No.2.1 Ploenchit Rd., Bangkok 10330, Thailand | **Tel:** +66(2)256923 & +66(2)2569908 | **Mobile/WhatsApp:** +33607591197 | **Email:** info@eiu.ac

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Introduction

Technology in today's world is evolving rapidly, day by day. Especially in the field of information technology and data science, there are 13 top technologies trends in 2024 has been written by Jaydeep Patadiya such as "Adaptive AI, Digital Immune System, AI Trust, Risk, and Security Management, Super App Development, Industrial Metaverse, Quantum Computing, Blockchain, IoT and Hyperconnectivity, Web 3.0, Sustainable Technology, Generative AI, Phygital Cnnvergence, Datafication" (Jaydeep-Patadiya, 2024).

In the field of Information Technology and Data Science, they have also actively contributed to the development of technology, as mentioned above. Data science is the study of problem-solving by researching, collecting, analyzing data to evaluate a phenomenon as a solution to these problems. It combines subjects such as math, statistics, research methodologies with programming, database management, artificial intelligence, machine learning and so on. They are also in high demand and well-paid because they work in both the business and IT sectors. Based on Marina Chatterjee, she said nowadays, data scientists work the following tasks, such as Data Analyst, Data Engineers, Database Administrator, Machine Learning Engineer, Data Scientist, Data Architect, Statistician, Business Analyst, Data and Analytics Manager (Chatterjee, 2024).

In this field, there is a course, Data Structure and Algorithm, which is an indispensable course. From medium.com as Logicmojo said, data structure and algorithm is one of the most course that play as important role in IT field and data science such as complex problem solving, enhance problem-solving abilities to create more efficient and scalable software (Logicmojo, 2024).

This report describes how to design and implement an efficient algorithm to solve a real-world problem that involves the use of data structures by using basic efficient algorithms following Blockchain Technology. A blockchain is a new type of database that is called shared database for records that are linked together by using cryptographic called hash or sometimes it can be called distributed ledger. Key features of blockchain are immutable, shared, distributed, and append only. Immutable means data one written, cannot be altered. Shared is the ledger shared among peers, and central authority does not own it. Distributed means data stored in a distributed format

which nodes having full or parties copies. Append only means data added to the ledger in append-only mode (Nevil, 2024).

Main Body

Problem Understanding

In traditional database management, data can be manipulated (CRUD) into tables by Structure Query Languages or data can be stored on any text file types but data cannot be guaranteed to be protected fully because there is no algorithm to protect it. But Blockchain Technology uses a combination of several data structures and algorithms to build a secure sensitive data. Data in Blockchain Technology cannot be hacked or compromised. Even though a cryptocurrency names Bitcoin is also use Blockchain algorithm (Srivastava, 2024).

Algorithm Design

The algorithms design is to build **Student Information Management System** by following the basic data structure and algorithms of Blockchain technology. Blockchain uses many features of data structure and algorithm including Linked List, Stack, Hash Function, Proof of Work, and so on.

Linked List is a type of abstract data type store the collection of nodes. Each node has two components, first is data and second is reference of the next node. It works linearly from the top to bottom sequentially. This way is what Blockchain uses to connect every block together like a chain.

Stack is an ADT (abstract data type) used similar to an array or a collection. It collects or stores value as its elements and it provides two functions such as push and pop. Push function is used to adds a new element or value to its collection. On the other hand, pop function is used to remove recently element that added to the existing collection. Stack can be called another name is LIFO (last in, first out). Blockchain use stack to add record from first to the last record connect every record by using previous hash value and current hash value. Records can be deleted from to last row, but not from the first or middle row (Marín, 2019).

Hash function is a complex mathematical formula that uses input normal string value to output hash string value by using secure hash algorithms (SHA). Its first version has developed since 1993 was SHA-0. Later on, it has been updating to SHA-1, SHA-2, and SHA-3. Blockchain uses hash function to calculate current record and also recalculate all records in the whole table to verify that all data is valid.

Proof of Work (PoW) is a consensus algorithm that blockchain used to validate or verify a whole transactions and add new blocks to the chain after all previous transaction are valid. Its work is recalculating each row value to new hash value and compare with existing hash value. This algorithm makes the Blockchain become a high security system because it recognizes valid or invalid data (Abrol, 2024).

Code Implementation

Student Information Management System is used PHP server-side language and **MySQL** database. This project features work by manipulation (CRUD) data with **StudentDB** database.

Step 1: In this project the database name is **StudentDB** and the there is a table name **TableStudents**. In the table, there are ten columns such as **recordID** column with integer type and primary key, **studentCode** column with varchar type, **firstName** column with varchar type, **lastName** column with varchar type, **sex** column with varchar type, **status** column with varchar type, **version** column with integer type, **previousRecordID** column with integer type, **previousHash** column with text type, and **currentHash** column with text type.

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Comments	Extra	Action
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 recordID	int(11)			No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 studentCode	varchar(255)	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 firstName	varchar(255)	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 lastName	varchar(255)	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	5 sex	varchar(255)	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	6 status	varchar(255)	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	7 version	int(11)			No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	8 previousRecordID	int(11)			No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	9 previousHash	text	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	10 currentHash	text	utf8mb4_general_ci		No	None			Change Drop More

Figure 1: Table and columns structure information

Step 2: This step is creating a connection file to store database connection information. The file name to store this information is **connection.php** with the PHP code below. But there is no output for the page.

```
<?php  
  
$hostName = "localhost";  
  
$userName="StudentUser";  
  
$password="Admin1111";  
  
$databaseName="StudentDB";  
  
?>
```

Step 3: This step is creating an insert feature to insert data from PHP page to MySQL database. Its file name is **insert.php** with code below.

```
<?php  
  
include("connection.php");  
  
$con = mysqli_connect($hostName,$userName,$password,$databaseName);  
  
if(!$con){  
  
    echo "Connect failed";  
  
}  
  
if(isset($_POST["buttonInsert"])){  
  
    $recordID=0;  
  
    $studentCode="";  
  
    $firstName = "";
```

```
$lastName = "";

$sex = "";

$status="";

$version = 0;

$previousRecordID=0;

$previousHash=0;

$currentHash="";

$qry = mysqli_query($con,'select * from tableStudents');

$totalRows = mysqli_num_rows($qry);

if($totalRows == 0){

    $recordID=1;

    $studentCode = $_POST["studentCode"];

    $firstName = $_POST["firstName"];

    $lastName = $_POST["lastName"];

    $sex = $_POST["sex"];

    $status="INSERT";

    $version = 1;

    $previousRecordID=0;

    $previousHash=0;
```

```

    $currentHash=
hash('sha256',$recordID.$studentCode.$firstName.$lastName.$sex.$status.$version.$previousRe
cordID.$previousHash);

}

elseif($totalRows > 0){

    $preQry=mysqli_query($con,'select * from tableStudents order by recordID desc limit 1');

    $preRow=mysqli_fetch_array($preQry,MYSQLI_ASSOC);

    $recordID=$preRow["recordID"]+1;

    $studentCode = $_POST["studentCode"];

    $firstName = $_POST["firstName"];

    $lastName = $_POST["lastName"];

    $sex = $_POST["sex"];

    $status="INSERT";

    $version = 1;

    $previousRecordID=0;

    $previousHash=$preRow["currentHash"];

    $currentHash=
hash('sha256',$recordID.$studentCode.$firstName.$lastName.$sex.$status.$version.$previousRe
cordID.$previousHash);

}

```

```
$qryInsert = mysqli_query($con,"insert into tableStudents values(

    ".$recordID.",

    ".$studentCode.",

    ".$firstName.",

    ".$lastName.",

    ".$sex.",

    ".$status.",

    ".$version.",

    ".$previousRecordID.",

    ".$previousHash.",

    ".$currentHash."

)") or die(mysqli_error($con));

if($qryInsert){

    header("location:select.php");

}

}

?>

<!DOCTYPE html>

<html lang="en">

<head>
```

```
<meta charset="UTF-8">
```

```
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
```

```
<title>Insert</title>
```

```
</head>
```

```
<body>
```

```
<form action="insert.php" method="post">
```

```
<table>
```

```
<tr>
```

```
<td><label>Student code </lable></td>
```

```
<td><input type="text" name="studentCode" required/></td>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
```

```
<td><label>First name </lable></td>
```

```
<td><input type="text" name="firstName" required/></td>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
```

```
<td><label>Last name </lable></td>
```

```
<td><input type="text" name="lastName" required/></td>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
```

```

        <td><label>Sex </lable></td>

        <td><input type="text" name="sex" required/></td>

    </tr>

    <tr>

        <td></td>

        <td><input type="submit" name="buttonInsert" value="Insert" /></td>

    </tr>

</table>

</form>

</body>

</html>

```

The result of the code above produces the output as the following figure.

Student code	<input type="text"/>
First name	<input type="text"/>
Last name	<input type="text"/>
Sex	<input type="text"/>
	<input type="submit" value="Insert"/>

Figure 2: The output of **insert.php** page on the browser

Step 3: This step is creating a page to display all records from **TableStudents** table of **StudentDB** database. The file name is **select.php** with the follow line of codes. And the delete feature codes also is being placed in the page as well.

```

<?php

include("connection.php");

$con = mysqli_connect($hostName,$userName,$password,$databaseName);

$valid=true;

if(!$con){

    echo "Connect failed";

}

if(isset($_GET["recordID"])){

    $preQry=mysqli_query($con,'select * from TableStudents order by recordID desc limit 1');

    $preRow=mysqli_fetch_array($preQry,MYSQLI_ASSOC);

    $recordID=$preRow["recordID"]+1;

    $previousHash=$preRow["currentHash"];

    $delQry=mysqli_query($con,'select * from TableStudents where
recordID='".$_GET["recordID"]."'');

    $delRow=mysqli_fetch_array($delQry,MYSQLI_ASSOC);

    $studentCode=$delRow["studentCode"];

    $firstName=$delRow["firstName"];

    $lastName = $delRow["lastName"];

    $sex =$delRow["sex"];

    $status = "DELETE";

```

```

$version = ($delRow["version"]+1);

$previousRecordID = $delRow["recordID"];

$currentHash=
hash('sha256',$recordID.$studentCode.$firstName.$lastName.$sex.$status.$version.$previousRe
cordID.$previousHash);

$queryInsert = mysqli_query($con,"insert into TableStudents values(

    ".$recordID.",

    ".$studentCode.",

    ".$firstName.",

    ".$lastName.",

    ".$sex.",

    ".$status.",

    ".$version.",

    ".$previousRecordID.",

    ".$previousHash.",

    ".$currentHash."

)") or die(mysqli_error($con));

if($queryInsert){

    header("location:select.php");

}

}

```

```

else{

    $qryStatus=mysqli_query($con,'select * from tableStudents order by recordID asc');

    while($row=mysqli_fetch_array($qryStatus,MYSQLI_ASSOC)){

        $recordID=$row["recordID"];

        $studentCode=$row["studentCode"];

        $firstName=$row["firstName"];

        $lastName=$row["lastName"];

        $sex=$row["sex"];

        $status=$row["status"];

        $version=$row["version"];

        $previousRecordID=$row["previousRecordID"];

        $previousHash=$row["previousHash"];

        $oldCurrentHash = $row["currentHash"];

        $currentHash=hash('sha256',$recordID.$studentCode.$firstName.$lastName.$sex.$status.$version.$previousRecordID.$previousHash);

        if(strcmp($oldCurrentHash,$currentHash)!=0){

            $valid = false;

            break;

        }

        else if(strcmp($oldCurrentHash,$currentHash)==0){

```

```
$qryLinkRow=mysqli_query($con,'SELECT * from TableStudents f INNER JOIN  
TableStudents s ON f.currentHash = s.previousHash');
```

```
$cnt = mysqli_num_rows($qryLinkRow);
```

```
if($cnt == 0){
```

```
    $valid = false;
```

```
    break;
```

```
}
```

```
else{
```

```
    $valid = true;
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

```
?>
```

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
```

```
<html lang="en">
```

```
<head>
```

```
    <meta charset="UTF-8">
```

```
    <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
```

```
    <title>Select</title>
```

```
</head>
```

```
<body>
```

```
<h3>Data is valid :<b><?php echo ($valid==true?"True":"False");?></b></h3>
```

```
<h3><a href="insert.php">Insert</a> </h3>
```

```
<table border=1>
```

```
<tr><th>Student Code</th>
```

```
<th>First Name</th>
```

```
<th>Last Name</th>
```

```
<th>Sex</th>
```

```
<th>Actions</th></tr>
```

```
<?php
```

```
$rowS= array();
```

```
$arrayS=array();
```

```
$qrySecond = mysqli_query($con,'SELECT * FROM tableStudents f INNER JOIN  
tableStudents s ON f.recordID = s.previousRecordID and f.recordID = s.previousRecordID');
```

```
while($rowSecond=mysqli_fetch_array($qrySecond,MYSQLI_ASSOC)){
```

```
array_push($rowS,$rowSecond);
```

```
}
```

```
for($i=0;$i<count($rowS);$i++){
```

```
$arrayS[$i]=$rowS[$i]["previousRecordID"];
```

```

    }

    $sids = implode('\, \' , $arrayS);

    $qryFirst = mysqli_query($con,"select * from tableStudents where status <> 'DELETE'
and recordID not in('".$sids."')");

    while($rowFirst=mysqli_fetch_array($qryFirst,MYSQLI_ASSOC)){

        echo '<tr>';

        echo '<td>'.$rowFirst["studentCode"]."</td>";

        echo "<td>".$rowFirst["firstName"]."</td>";

        echo "<td>".$rowFirst["lastName"]."</td>";

        echo "<td>".$rowFirst["sex"]."</td>";

        echo '<td><a href="edit.php?recordID='.$rowFirst["recordID"].'">Edit</a> | ';

        echo '<a href="?'recordID='.$rowFirst["recordID"].'">Delete</a></td>';

        echo '</tr>';

    }

    ?>

</table>

</body>

</html>

```

The result of line of codes above produces the output as below figure.

Data is valid :True

Insert

Student Code	First Name	Last Name	Sex	Actions
st001	mony	ho	male	Edit Delete
st002	seyha	ly	male	Edit Delete
st003	tana	ban	male	Edit Delete

Figure 3: The output of **select.php** page on the browser

Step 4: This step is creating a page name **edit.php** to edit records in **TableStudents** table in **StudentDB** database.

```
<?php
include("connection.php");

$con = mysqli_connect($hostName,$userName,$password,$databaseName);

if(!$con){
    echo "Connect failed";
}

if(isset($_GET["recordID"])){
    $preQry=mysqli_query($con,"select * from TableStudents where
recordID='".$_GET["recordID"]."'");

    $preRow=mysqli_fetch_array($preQry,MYSQLI_ASSOC);

    $recordID = $preRow["recordID"];
```

```

$studentCode = $preRow["studentCode"];

$firstName = $preRow["firstName"];

$lastName = $preRow["lastName"];

$sex = $preRow["sex"];

$version = $preRow["version"];

}

if(isset($_POST["buttonUpdate"])){

    $preQry=mysqli_query($con,'select * from TableStudents order by recordID desc limit 1');

    $preRow=mysqli_fetch_array($preQry,MYSQLI_ASSOC);

    $recordID=$preRow["recordID"]+1;

    $studentCode = $_POST["studentCode"];

    $firstName = $_POST["firstName"];

    $lastName = $_POST["lastName"];

    $sex = $_POST["sex"];

    $status="UPDATE";

    $version = $_POST["version"]+1;

    $previousRecordID=$_POST["recordID"];

    $previousHash=$preRow["currentHash"];

    $currentHash=
hash('sha256',$recordID.$studentCode.$firstName.$lastName.$sex.$status.$version.$previousRe
cordID.$previousHash);

```

```

$qryInsert = mysqli_query($con,"insert into TableStudents values(

    ".$recordID.",

    ".$studentCode.",

    ".$firstName.",

    ".$lastName.",

    ".$sex.",

    ".$status.",

    ".$version.",

    ".$previousRecordID.",

    ".$previousHash.",

    ".$currentHash."

)") or die(mysqli_error($con));

if($qryInsert){

    header("location:select.php");

}

}

?>

<!DOCTYPE html>

<html lang="en">

<head>

```

```
<meta charset="UTF-8">
```

```
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
```

```
<title>Edit</title>
```

```
</head>
```

```
<body>
```

```
<form action="edit.php" method="post">
```

```
<table>
```

```
<tr style="display:none">
```

```
<td><label>Student ID </lable></td>
```

```
<td><input type="hidden" name="recordID" value='<?php echo $recordID;?>' /></td>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
```

```
<td><label>Student code </lable></td>
```

```
<td><input type="text" name="studentCode" value='<?php echo $studentCode;?>'
```

```
/></td>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
```

```
<td><label>First name </lable></td>
```

```
<td><input type="text" name="firstName" value='<?php echo $firstName;?>' /></td>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
<tr>

    <td><label>Last name </lable></td>

    <td><input type="text" name="lastName" value='<?php echo $lastName;?>' /></td>

</tr>

<tr>

    <td><label>Sex </lable></td>

    <td><input type="text" name="sex" value='<?php echo $sex;?>' /></td>

</tr>

<tr style="display:none">

    <td><label>Version </lable></td>

    <td><input type="hidden" name="version" value='<?php echo $version;?>' /></td>

</tr>

<tr>

    <td></td>

    <td><input type="submit" name="buttonUpdate" value="Update" /></td>

</tr>

</table>

</form>

</body>

</html>
```

The source code of **edit.php** page produces the output as below figure.

Student code	<input type="text" value="st001"/>
First name	<input type="text" value="mony"/>
Last name	<input type="text" value="ho"/>
Sex	<input type="text" value="male"/>
	<input type="button" value="Update"/>

Figure 4: The output of **edit.php** page on the browser

Testing and Evaluation

First testing: Start a browser and access **insert.php** page to insert data such as student code, first name, last name, and sex. Then click **Insert** button to save the data.

Student code	<input type="text" value="st001"/>
First name	<input type="text" value="mony"/>
Last name	<input type="text" value="ho"/>
Sex	<input type="text" value="male"/>
	<input type="button" value="Insert"/>

Figure 5: Output of **insert.php** page

After succeeded, it will be redirected to **select.php** page. And data in the table below has three records of student information. in Data in valid section, it shows **True** because data has been inserted correctly.

Data is valid :True

Insert

Student Code	First Name	Last Name	Sex	Actions
st001	mony	ho	male	Edit Delete
st002	seyha	ly	male	Edit Delete
st003	tana	ban	male	Edit Delete

Figure 6: All data from **TableStudents** displays on **select.php** page

Second testing: When **Delete** link has been clicked, for example on **st003** row, its row will be disappeared look like it has been deleted from the **TableStudents** table.

Data is valid :True

Insert

Student Code	First Name	Last Name	Sex	Actions
st001	mony	ho	male	Edit Delete
st002	seyha	ly	male	Edit Delete

Figure 7: Student code number **st003** has been deleted from the table of page.

Even though student code **st003** has been disappeared from the web page. But in the table of database is still stored. This way follows the Blockchain concept that transaction cannot be modified, just append only. In table, student code is **st003**, is being marked as **DELETE** in **status** column.

recordID	studentCode	firstName	lastName	sex	status	version	previousRecordID	previousHash	currentHash
1	st001	mony	ho	male	INSERT	1	0	0	01c4f98605388a4dc5027adec6d2bcd22355dfe0cbfdb3bc73...
2	st002	seyha	ly	male	INSERT	1	0	01c4f98605388a4dc5027adec6d2bcd22355dfe0cbfdb3bc73...	f6737d97d58b8769f7c26d0e500117ace54bf5037235146b73...
3	st003	tana	ban	male	INSERT	1	0	f6737d97d58b8769f7c26d0e500117ace54bf5037235146b73...	4faf64efefbf2187a47cb35aba6f65ba5b9d450cbac258fa67...
4	st003	tana	ban	male	DELETE	2	3	4faf64efefbf2187a47cb35aba6f65ba5b9d450cbac258fa67...	54767b88376e3b

Figure 8: student code **st003** is still stores in the table without deleting

Third testing: When **Edit** link has been clicked, it will be redirected to **edit.php** to allows users to edit the existing information. For example, student code **st002** row has been clicked on **Edit** link, so **edit.php** will be displayed with the existing information of its rows. The user can edit this information such as **student code**, **first name**, **last name** and **sex**.

Student code

First name

Last name

Sex

➔

Update to

Student code

First name

Last name

Sex

Figure 9: Inputting new value to update student code **st002**

After clicking **Update** button, data of student code **st002** has been updated first name to **hasey** and last name is **ny**.

Data is valid :True

Insert

Student Code	First Name	Last Name	Sex	Actions
st001	mony	ho	male	Edit Delete
st002	hasey	ny	male	Edit Delete

Figure 10: Student code **st002** shows updated data on the table

After updated, data in table of database does not update but it adds the updated data to new row in **TableStudents** table by marking **UPDATE** in **status** column. This way makes all records can

be tracing from the first row to the last row. And in **previousRecordID** column stores the **recordID** value that connect to the previous original row (row number 2) look like a linked lists that is used by Blockchain theory.

recordID	studentCode	firstName	lastName	sex	status	version	previousRecordID	previousHash	currentHash
1	st001	mony	ho	male	INSERT	1	0	0	01c4f98605388a4dc5027adec6d2bcd22355dfe0cbfdb3bc73...
2	st002	seyha	ly	male	INSERT	1	0	01c4f98605388a4dc5027adec6d2bcd22355dfe0cbfdb3bc73...	f6737d97d58b8769f
3	st003	tana	ban	male	INSERT	1	0	f6737d97d58b8769f7c26d0e500117ace54bf5037235146b73...	4faf64efefbf2187a47
4	st003	tana	ban	male	DELETE	2	3	4faf64efefbf2187a47cb35aba6f65ba5b9d450cbac258fa67...	54767b88376e3b10:
5	st002	hasey	ny	male	UPDATE	2	2	54767b88376e3b1027264694acd6797d068a2ad061a3dbe892...	65b9f13be1144da5b

Figure 11: In **status** column of student code **st002** shows **DELETE**

Fourth testing: if a database administrator or a hacker can access to modify data in the table, for example he or she changes **student code** number **5** from **male** to **female**. The database works normally even though data has been modified.

recordID	studentCode	firstName	lastName	sex	status	version	previousRecordID	previousHash	currentHash
1	st001	mony	ho	male	INSERT	1	0	0	01c4f98605388a4dc5027adec6d2bcd22355dfe0cbfdb3bc73...
2	st002	seyha	ly	male	INSERT	1	0	01c4f98605388a4dc5027adec6d2bcd22355dfe0cbfdb3bc73...	f6737d97d58b8769f
3	st003	tana	ban	male	INSERT	1	0	f6737d97d58b8769f7c26d0e500117ace54bf5037235146b73...	4faf64efefbf2187a47
4	st003	tana	ban	male	DELETE	2	3	4faf64efefbf2187a47cb35aba6f65ba5b9d450cbac258fa67...	54767b88376e3b10:
5	st002	hasey	ny	female	UPDATE	2	2	54767b88376e3b1027264694acd6797d068a2ad061a3dbe892...	65b9f13be1144da5b

Figure 12: Row number **5** has been modified **sex** column from **male** to **female**

But this system has a consensus algorithm is called Proof-of-Work. It always recalculates all data in each row to generate new hash value and verify with the existing hash value. In this case, because of **st002** has been changed **sex** value from **male** to **female** so data right now is invalid. The message at the top displays **Data is valid: False**.

Data is valid :False

Insert

Student Code	First Name	Last Name	Sex	Actions
st001	mony	ho	male	Edit Delete
st002	hasey	ny	female	Edit Delete

Figure 13: On **select.php** page shows data is invalid

But when the **sex** column of student code **st002** has been modified back to **male**, so the consensus algorithm will provide the information of data in table is valid.

recordID	studentCode	firstName	lastName	sex	status	version	previousRecordID	previousHash	currentHash
1	st001	mony	ho	male	INSERT	1	0	0	01c4f98605388a4dc5027adec6d2bcd22355dfe0cbfdb3bc73...
2	st002	seyha	ly	male	INSERT	1	0	01c4f98605388a4dc5027adec6d2bcd22355dfe0cbfdb3bc73...	f6737d97d58b8;
3	st003	tana	ban	male	INSERT	1	0	f6737d97d58b8769f7c26d0e500117ace54bf5037235146b73...	4fa64efefbf218;
4	st003	tana	ban	male	DELETE	2	3	4fa64efefbf2187a47cb35aba6f65ba5b9d450cbac258fa67...	54767b88376e3
5	st002	hasey	ny	male	UPDATE	2	2	54767b88376e3b1027264694acd6797d068a2ad061a3dbe892...	65b9f13be1144c

Figure 14: Row number **5** has been modified **sex** column from **female** to **male**

In **select.php** page displays **Data is valid: True**, this means that right now data in the table is valid.

Data is valid :True

Insert

Student Code	First Name	Last Name	Sex	Actions
st001	mony	ho	male	Edit Delete
st002	hasey	ny	male	Edit Delete

Figure 15: One **select.php** page shows data is valid

Fifth testing: If someone delete a row, for example **recordID** number 3, so this action will break the chain of the transactions.

recordID	studentCode	firstName	lastName	sex	status	version	previousRecordID	previousHash	currentHash
1	st001	mony	ho	male	INSERT	1	0	0	01c4f98605388
2	st002	seyha	ly	male	INSERT	1	0	01c4f98605388a4dc5027adec6d2bcd22355dfe0cbfdb3bc73...	f6737d97d58b8
4	st003	tana	ban	male	DELETE	2	3	4faf64efefbf2187a47cb35aba6f65ba5b9d450cbac258fa67...	54767b88376e
5	st002	hasey	ny	male	UPDATE	2	2	54767b88376e3b1027264694acd6797d068a2ad061a3dbe892...	65b9f13be1144

Figure 16: The **recordID** number 3 will be deleted from the table

In **select.php** page alerts that the data in the table is invalid. At the top shows the message **Data is valid: False** because someone compromised data in the table of database directly.

Data is valid :False

Insert

Student Code	First Name	Last Name	Sex	Actions
st001	mony	ho	male	Edit Delete
st002	hasey	ny	male	Edit Delete

Figure 17: On **select.php** page shows data is invalid

Conclusion

Data structure and algorithm is the most important course in information technology or data science field. Its theory can be applied in almost all sectors especially in application development. Even though new technology grows rapidly, data structure and algorithm is still used along to it.

Blockchain technology is an actual case that it is a new technology but the core concept is come from data structure and algorithm. So, data structure and algorithm plays as an important role for many fields such as IT, Data Science, Researching, or Data Analysis.

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ITDS420 - Assignment Rubric

Student's Full Name: Mony Ho

EIU ID: EIU95527

Category	Marks Allocation	Marks Attained	Comments
1. Problem Understanding	10 marks	8	
2. Algorithm Design	20 marks	17	
3. Code Implementation	30 marks	25	
4. Testing and Evaluation	20 marks	17	
5. Report and Presentation	20 marks	16	
<p>*** Penalty *** This penalty is for papers that do not meet the assignment requirements. (i.e. word count, format, etc.)</p>	(-5)		
Total marks allocated and achieved:	100 marks	83	

The assignment is presented nicely with all headings and explanation demonstrating the understanding well enough.

Additional Remarks:

Some minor grammatical and spelling errors were found like use of tenses and verbs.